

Importance of Arts Culture in Society

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The importance of culture in society can be depicted by the giving an example:

LAI HARAوبا

Lai-Haraوبا is celebrated in honour of the sylvan deities known as Umang-Lais, meaning deities of calm and quite environment of beautiful forests. The festival represents the worship of traditional deities and ancestors of the Manipuri society. It is usually observed during the month of Kalen tha (summer season). The festival is a part of recollection of the creation stories played by the deities with the first origin of this universe and evolution of the plants and animals through the will of AtiyaShidaba. Translated, Lai Haraوبا means "merry making of the Gods" in Meetei.

There are six major types of Lai Haraوبا. The differences in the six festivals are very wide and broad; however, the overall theme is the same. The differences are in the variations of processes and in cultural aspects and not in the inner wisdom and basis of the philosophy of Lai Haraوبا. The different types are:

Kanglei (Imphal) Haraوبا
ChakpaHaraوبا
Andro Haraوبا
Sekmai Haraوبا
Moirang Haraوبا
Kakching Haraوبا

Celebration

The complete festival begins in the day time of the second day. It has about twenty steps or items in it. Laiboulathaba is the most important part of the beginning of laiboushaba

ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to show how Arts Culture gives an important education to the society. Through the different culture, a child many thing which are not learn in academic environment and understand their origin and significance of different culture. It influence is society to bring peace and harmony of one community to another community.

KEYWORDS: Culture, Festival and Ritual Ceremony, Relation with Society.

INTRODUCTION

Culture refers to the cumulative deposit of knowledge, experience, beliefs, values, attitudes, meanings, hierarchies, religion, notions of time, roles, spatial relations, concepts of the universe, and material objects and possessions acquired by a group of people in the course of generations through individual and group striving.

Different culture has different meaning relating to origin

- Kut festival is celebrated by the Kuki-Chin-Mizo groups of Manipur. It takes place on 1st November in honor of an abundant harvest.
- Gang-Ngai is a festival lasting five days. It starts with the omen taking ceremony which is later continued with dance and feast.
- Cheiraوبا is the Manipur New Year which takes place in April. As part of the traditional belief, the villagers climb the nearest hill which helps in bringing good fortune.
- Yaosang is like the festival of Holi which is considered the most important festival in Manipur. The locals take part in the celebration of merrymaking.

(creation of the Universe and the synthesis of the human body).

A plantain leaf on the specific place represents the unseen God manifesting the world. The maibi with all the participants who also join in the laikouba and lei langba should move around the plantain leaf three times symbolising the manifestations of MangnagShidaba, LuwangShidaba, and Khuman Shidaba (clan deities). After this the maiba and maibis stand erect before the deity and pray for the beginning of the laibou. At this time no one should move, speak and change his/her position. No one could come in or out of the laibung during this item, Hoirou Haya Laوبا.

The maibi begins to move in the form of the Khayomjagoi (a dance with hands at the level of the navel) with the HoirouHaya hymn. When the maibi sings Hayingeinanoibadimeinawainanoiye; he tangnashamnanoiye, all the participants begin to move their footsteps without dancing their hands and body. In laiboushaba the maibi narrates with hymns and dances the creation of this universe; the sun, the stars, the planets, the moon, the earth, air, water, etc. After making this earth inhabitable, the dances shows the creation of all beings including man. In the case of man, the different parts: the hand, the fingers, the palms, the arms, the head, the neck, the eyes, the body, the thigh, the feet, the toes, and all the other parts are made with the hymns and dances in different khut-theks (hand movements).

There are sixty four important khut-theks (hand gestures) for making the human body. All are shown with very fine, attractive and meaningful dances representing the development of the human body in twelve months in the parents' womb. Then the building of houses, starting of agriculture and other stages of human development are played. The last part of the dance confines with the songs, paoshaisheis, for the welfare of all the individuals. The control of lust, keeping strict discipline of celibacy and control of the mind are very clearly and forcefully sung to remind all the participants the importance and the value of life in this human birth.

LaienMathek and chongkhonglitpa are played to represent the continuity of human life. Kanglei-thokpa or lai-lam-thokpa is a play of the festival performed outside the laibung, in any place suitable for assembling greater number of participants.

Lairoi (the end of haraoba) is very important and it includes performances: OugriHangen (the song of the control of mind) Khencho(the concept of the third birth or the next birth or the human birth) *HijanHirao* (the song of cutting big trees for two big boats: one for the male deity, the other for the female deity and with which boat race is held) are sung On the next day of lairoi, Mukna (Meetei wrestling), kangjei (meetei Field like hockey/polo), and races are held and prizes are given to those who win in the competitions of sports and games. Thus, Lai Haraoba is the only cultural activity in which social, philosophical and religious life of the Meiteis are depicted very deeply and carefully. With this cultural activity, the continuous thought of the people of this culturally rich land is preserved from the long gone days never decaying and fading.

Relationship of arts with culture in society

Art influences society by changing opinions, instilling values and translating experiences across space and time. Research has shown art affects the fundamental sense of self.

Painting, sculpture, music, literature and the other arts are often considered to be the repository of a society's collective memory. Art preserves what fact-based historical records

cannot: how it felt to exist in a particular place at a particular time.

Art in this sense is communication; it allows people from different cultures and different times to communicate with each other via images, sounds and stories. Art is often a vehicle for social change. It can give voice to the politically or socially disenfranchised. A song, film or novel can rouse emotions in those who encounter it, inspiring them to rally for change.

Art also has utilitarian influences on society. There is a demonstrable, positive correlation between schoolchildren's grades in math and literacy, and their involvement with drama or music activities.

CONCLUSION

The importance of art culture in society plays a very important role. Through the different culture, a child learns many things which are not learn in academic environment such as the significance of dress i.e Meitei community wears phanekmayeknaibi in marriage ceremony or in any festivals and pongouphanek in death ceremony. Likewise the Muslim wear burkha and tribal people have to attend church every Sunday. These kind of knowledge is being taught through culture. When one have better knowledge of one's own culture they will understand their origin and the significance of their culture. Likewise knowledge of different culture will make the person understand many things.

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